

Quantum Conservation and Invariance and $i\hbar/dt$ and $-\hbar/dx$ Operators

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It was argued in (1) that Fermat's least time principle for light (in a two dimensional (x,y) reflection or refraction scenario) minimizes time by actually varying it in terms of a spatially invariant variable i.e. x (i.e. taking d/dx) with the flat face of the mirror/medium along the x axis at $y=0$. This is equivalent to conserving momentum in the x direction. Thus d/dx is associated with (px) which may be associated with the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$. In other words, d/dx emerges as a momentum operator (up to a factor) and d/dt as an energy operator, yet both are generators in time and space linked with invariance of constant values i.e. conservation. Furthermore an eigenvalue equation: $-\hbar/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$ and $i\hbar/dt \exp(-iEt) = E \exp(-iEt)$ automatically (by the nature of eigenvalue) leads to orthogonal eigenfunctions linked to conservation of energy and momentum.

In special relativity rest mass m_0 represents a constant in time which may exist at any point x . In fact, it is often thought of as a point, for example a center of mass point. The actual object with m_0 , however, may be large with moving parts all within a "container". What then does x,t in $-Et+px$ mean for constant E,p ? It seems that x,t are center-of-mass coordinates for the overall system. We argued in previous notes that $1/p$ is proportional to a wavelength so for $p \rightarrow 0$, m_0 may be at any x point with the same probability. Within the system with moving parts, however, there is motion and an x scale for each moving piece. For a single particle bound system, there is a single energy at each x which is like m_0 and a potential $V(x)$ and $KE(x)$.

In (2) we argued that given the free particle relationship $E^2 - p^2 = -m_0^2$ ($c=1$) one may retain a constant E value by replacing E with $E-V(x)$ and p with $\langle p \rangle$ (and not $\langle p \rangle \langle p \rangle$). How do the probabilities appear? They are linked to $-Et+px$ with frequency \hbar/E and wavelength \hbar/p and are specifically manifested by $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$. For $\langle p \rangle$ and $\langle p^2 \rangle$ we use spatial probabilities i.e. $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Each $\exp(ipx)$ is linked to the operator $-\hbar/dx$ and invariance, but p^2 is linked with the operator $-\hbar^2/dx^2$ and one does not use an eigenfunction of this operator. Thus the notion of conservation of momentum is retained in the $\exp(ipx)$ s and their linear combination $W(x)$ yields a function such that an average kinetic energy exists at each x point i.e. $KE(x) = KE_{classical} = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$. This is combined with a $V(x)$ to ensure constant E at each x point i.e. create a kind of m_0 piece linked with $i\hbar/dt$. We argue that E being constant at each x is a statistical equilibrium type of result. Each $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with an average motion of $x=p/m t$ and given that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are included, there is also the notion of $\langle p \rangle$ which is positive and negative in different regions and integrates to 0. $\langle p^2 \rangle$ from $\langle p \rangle$ becomes the classical $p(x)$.

Thus bound state quantum mechanics seems to be based on a free particle treatment which follows from the special relativistic Lorentz invariants $E^2 - p^2 = -m_0^2$ and $-Et+px = \text{constant}$, directly linked to conservation ideas. Conservation of momentum of an internal bound particle is maintained through $\exp(ipx)$, while $\langle p^2 \rangle$ by itself is not linked with conservation as there is no eigenstate, but is combined with a $V(x)$ to create a constant E_n linked with the entire system (and $P=0$) which then becomes associated with invariance in time and the generator $i\hbar/dt$.

In this note, we try to argue that the notion of $W^*(x)W(x)$ (where $W(x)=\text{wavefunction}=\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$) is spatial density and $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$ based on spatial invariance and

conservation of momentum for a single particle bound state even though there seems to be no spatial invariance or notion of conservation of momentum in $W(x)$ which is simply a solution of the time-independent Schrodinger equation. One may move from a $W(x)$ scenario (i.e. Schrodinger equation) to a $W^*(x)W(x)$ picture, by trying to “pick out” invariant (p only terms) using the orthogonality of the $\exp(ipx)$ s. Thus $W^*(x)W(x)$ (spatial density) emerges naturally in this approach.

Invariance and Quantum Momentum and Energy Operators

We argued in (1) that the notion of $C1 \frac{d}{dx}$ ($C1=\text{constant}$) acting as a momentum operator linked to conservation of momentum in the x direction already appears in Fermat’s least time principle. In particular if one consider a two dimensional reflection or refraction problem with the flat mirror/medium’s face along the x axis at $y=0$, then minimization of time is realized by taking d/dx of t_1+t_2 expressed in terms of x , a spatially invariant variable, and leads to conservation of momentum in the x direction. Thus the generator of translations d/dx in a spatially invariant direction is associated with momentum in that direction and ultimately its conservation. In fact, one may write $A = (px) x$ such that $dA(x)/dx + dA(L-x)/dx = 0$ where $A(x) = \sqrt{xx + YY}$. $(px)x$ is also equivalent to $-i \ln(\exp(ipx))$ which may be considered as the information associated with the dynamical complex probability $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ is two dimensional because time has been removed and one needs two dimensions to describe the direction of motion.

Thus we argued in (1) that the ideas of free particle quantum mechanics are contained in Fermat’s principle (which we assume also holds for particles with rest mass) and is linked to the Lorentz invariant $-Et + p \cdot r$.

One may point out, however, that the ideas of invariance and conservation of momentum apply to the two dimensional reflection/refraction problem. This begs the question: Why should $\exp(ipx)$ be somehow linked to a one dimensional single particle bound state problem? There seems to be neither conservation of momentum nor spatial invariance in the bound state problem. Thus we wish to discuss this problem further.

Special Relativity

Special relativity includes the two 4-vectors (x,t) and (p,E) for a free particle. It also utilizes the concept of a rest mass (for a particle, not for light). A point we wish to make is that m_0 may be applied to a complicated system consisting of many moving parts. For example a piece of classical matter has a temperature and moving electrons, nucleons etc, yet is considered to be a static piece of mass. This idea may be extended to include a box containing moving objects. This then begs the question: What do x and t represent? It seems they apply to the center of mass of the object with rest mass m_0 . m_0 is considered to be constant in time and may exist at any x point, Thus there is a kind of spatial invariance associated with it. Any x point has the same probability.

If one considers the free particle Lorentz invariant $-Et + px = A$ then $A=0$ at the following points: $t = \hbar n / E$ and $x = \hbar n / p$ where n is an integer. This, we have argued in previous notes, is the basis for a frequency and wavelength i.e. an internal clock and ruler (functions of $E = pp/2m$ and

p). Like in Fermat's least time principle, one has $dA/dx = p$ and spatial invariance. There is, however, no conservation of momentum except for the notion that an eigenvalue equation:

$$-i\hbar/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((1))$$

automatically creates orthogonal functions $\exp(ipx)$. ((1)) may be applied to time to yield another set of orthogonal functions:

$$i\hbar/dt \exp(-iEt) = E \exp(-iEt) \quad ((2))$$

Thus for a free particle there is invariance in space and time and also unusual dynamical probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$.

Why do eigenfunctions ensure orthogonality or conservation of momentum over space?

$$\int dx (-i\hbar/dx) (\exp(-ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x)) = (-i\hbar) \exp(-ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) \Big|_{x=0}^{x=L} + (p_1 - p_2) \int dx \exp(-ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) \quad ((3))$$

$(p_2 - p_1)$ cannot be zero for differing p_1, p_2 so the overlap integral, linked to conservation of momentum is zero, if the function evaluated at the endpoints is zero. (Formally, one may show that the integral of $\exp(-ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) dx$ as well. (3)).

Thus creating an eigenvalue equation automatically guarantees orthogonal functions which in turn express conservation i.e. the overlap in space of an eigenfunction representing one value, with another is zero. An operator (i.e a potential) would be needed to allow for overlap.

Thus the free particle case makes use of $-Et + px$ to create eigenfunctions of $-i\hbar/dx$ i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ which are orthogonal ensuring momentum conservation. A similar consideration holds for E i.e. $i\hbar/dt$, $\exp(-iEt)$ and energy conservation. A main question, however, remains as to how these should be applied to a single bound particle.

A Single Particle Bound State

Consider a single particle bound in a potential $V(x)$. In such a case, it seems there is no spatial invariance or momentum conservation. In fact, one would normally extend the free particle Lorentz invariant:

$$-E^2 + p^2 = -m_0^2 c^4 \quad \text{to} \quad -(E - V(x))^2 + p(x)^2 = -m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((4))$$

To represent a constant E and a $p(x)$ i.e. a different free particle p at each x . In the nonrelativistic case: $E = p^2/2m_0 + V(x)$ i.e. Newtonian mechanics. $-Et + px$ and the associated $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ seem to apply to a free particle i.e. predict a frequency and wavelength which may be observed in diffraction/interference experiments. Why should these free particle ideas be extended to a bound state problem?

We first revisit the idea of m_0 (rest mass) representing a complicated system with many moving parts. If the overall system is not moving i.e. translating in space, then X, T represent center-of-mass coordinates for an overall energy $m_0 c^2$ and $P=0$. Using the idea of wavelength \hbar/P implies that for $P=0$ the center of mass has the same probability to exist at any x point. We also note that ((4)) creates a constant E at each x point which has the appearance of a statistical equilibrium. Thus E , being constant, should be associated with a free particle $\exp(-iEt)$. There would also be an $\exp(iPx)$ with $P=0$. What about the internal motion of the bound particle? Given that E is constant there is no need for time considerations, but only spatial ones. The question which arises is: Why would one not use ((4)) or its Newtonian nonrelativistic limit?

$$p^2/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((5))$$

We argue that given that $\exp(-iEt)$ still applies, which follows from $-Et+px$, one should retain the notion of energy following from either $i\hbar d/dt$ or $-1/2m d^2/dx^2$. In this case there is not a single $\exp(ipx)$ which has the same $p^2/2m$ at all x , but rather a function $-1/2m d^2W/dx^2 / W$ which when added to $V(x)$ yields E at all x . $W(x)$ is in the form of a probability and dividing by W normalizes the result.

Thus even though $-i\hbar d/dx$ is the generator of translations and associated with invariance in space, $-d^2/dx^2$ is the p^2 operator and $W(x)$ is not its eigenfunction. Thus there is no invariance associated with $-d^2/dx^2$. Invariance is created by adding $-1/2m d^2W/dx^2 / W$ to $V(x)$ to create a constant energy E at all x . One may note, however, that an orthogonal set of eigenfunctions for $-i\hbar d/dx$ exist which may be used as a basis for $W(x)$. Thus even though $W(x)$ is not an invariant, it is composed of a linear combination of spatially invariant $\exp(ipx)$, each of which ensures its own conservation of momentum when integrated over x . Thus:

$$W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \text{ constant} \quad ((6))$$

The constant is introduced so that $\exp(ipx)$ constant's are orthonormal.

One may ask whether there is any physical reason for ((6)). It seems there is as one may knock out a bound state particle placing it in a free state described by $\exp(-iEt+px)$ where $E=p^2/2m$. What should the probability be for a given p ? $W(x)$ is ultimately defined in the time-independent Schrodinger equation as a function such that $-1/2m d^2W/dx^2 / W (=KE(x))$ when added to $V(x)$ yields a constant E . It is not a priori defined in terms of $\exp(ipx)$ s in this scenario and there is no spatial invariance or momentum conservation associated with $KE(x)$ by itself.

Given that the operator $-d^2/dx^2$ is used, however, $-i\hbar d/dx$ must represent momentum, but $W(x)$ is not a momentum eigenstate. Nevertheless one may define:

$$-i\hbar dW/dx/W \quad ((7))$$

Given that $-i\hbar d/dx$ has eigenfunctions $\exp(ipx)$ which are manifest when a bound particle is knocked from a potential and using ((6)) one must somehow create probabilities for various p

values. Using the notion of conservation of momentum i.e. orthogonal $\exp(ipx)$ values, one has the mathematical result:

$$\int W^*(x)W(x)dx = \sum_p a^*(p)a(p) \quad (8)$$

If $W(x)$ is normalized to 1, then $a^*(p)a(p)$'s represent probabilities. $W^*(x)W(x)$ then seems to represent physical density.

Thus the conservation of momentum/orthogonality feature of the $\exp(ipx)$ s is key in obtaining the physical observable $P(p)$. This is further linked to the idea that $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ i.e. all x points are equal which is a physically observable invariance feature of a particle moving at a constant speed. In order to obtain the physical observable $P(p)$, one must deal at the same level i.e. a $W^*(x)W(x)$ level which automatically leads to $\exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$ terms, which contribute to a local $W^*(x)W(x)$ ultimately disappearing from the integral, which being over all space picks up the spatially invariant combinations.

Thus we argue that conservation and spatial invariance is a key idea associated with $W^*(x)W(x)$ representing a physical observable (i.e. spatial density). The broken invariance created by mixed terms $\exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$, however, is critical to creating the multiple hump shape of $W^*(x)W(x)$. This hump shape, however, is also linked to the $-d/dx$ d/dx operator which is not linked with conservation of momentum or invariance. Thus even though the solution of $W(x)$ from the time-independent Schrodinger equation is not based on invariance or momentum conservation, it seems that the formation of $W^*(x)W(x)$ as spatial density is (and of $a^*(p)a(p)$ as $P(p)$). In the next section we consider a more direct approach to linking $W(x)$ (not invariant) with $W^*(x)W(x)$ which when integrated over dx brings out a sum of invariant terms (i.e. p terms).

Kinetic Energy Versus Kinetic Energy Density

$\exp(ipx)$ is a dynamic probability, i.e. linked to motion, and provides information about motion at a specific x point. $\exp(ipx)$ is complex with the real and imaginary parts taking on both positive and negative values. Within a wavelength \hbar/p there is no time, but on average the particle moves according to: $x=p/m t$. $\exp(ipx)$ or a linear combination of these are able to create $W(x)$ or any x dependent average i.e. $\langle pp \rangle = -d/dx dW/dx / W$. No $W^*(x)$ or conservation/invariance has been considered. In fact the interference of various $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(ip_1x)$ terms in $W(x)$ breaks spatial invariance.

In the above section, however, we considered $\int W^*(x)W(x)$ which becomes a sum over p which does not interfere i.e. the spatial invariance is restored which is fine because x is no longer in the picture. $\int W^*(x)W(x)dx = \sum_p a^*(p)a(p) = 1$. This begs the question: What is: $\sum_p a^*(p)a(p) p^2/2m$?

Formally this is: $\int dx W^*(x)W(x) \{-1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W\}$ i.e. \int spatial density * $KE(x) dx$. This quantity is usually not calculated classically. If one tries to introduce a classical density proportional to dt , this is still not identical to the quantum picture as quantum density $W^*(x)W(x)$ always has humps (for say an oscillator regardless of the energy level). Thus spatial density multiplied by kinetic energy, with both functions of x breaking spatial invariance, when

integrated over x yields an invariant picture i.e. a sum of p type terms. How does this spatially invariant result follow from an invariant one?

Consider writing the time independent Schrodinger equation i.e. the non- spatially invariant equation with $W(x)$ in terms of $V(x)=\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ and $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ constant (where the constant is needed to so $\exp(ipx)$ constant in orthonormal).

Collecting coefficients of $\exp(ipx)$ s (which are orthogonal) yields:

$$a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) = E_n a(p) \quad ((9))$$

Thus one has an invariant type equation in the sense that it contains a single $a(p)$. This is equivalent to the equation:

$$a(p) \left(-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \right) \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx) + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) = E_n \quad ((10))$$

((10)) is the equation of a free particle $\exp(ipx)$ in a constant potential $\sum_k V_k a(p-k)$, but this potential depends on the entire set of $a(p)$ values. Thus one has a coupled set of invariant $\exp(ipx)$ s as already known from $W(x)=\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ constant.

We now note that in order to obtain ((9)) one picks the coefficient of $\exp(ipx)$ because the $\exp(ipx)$ s are orthogonal. Thus ((9)) does not contain x . A similar mathematical approach would be to multiply by $\exp(-ipx)$ or $a^*(p)\exp(-ipx)$ and integrate over x . This then leads to:

$$a^*(p)a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} + a^*(p) \sum_k V_k a(p-k) = E_n a^*(p)a(p) \quad ((11))$$

Thus one need not introduce $W^*(x)W(x)$ in a somewhat ad hoc manner and integrate although in ((11)) one is doing essentially the same thing. The invariant pieces $\exp(ipx)$ which conserve momentum and display spatial invariance are present, but one needs $\exp(-ipx)$ or $a^*(p)\exp(-ipx)$ to "pull" them out. This is why one has dynamic averages $\langle p^2 \rangle = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$ which depend on the dynamic probabilities $\exp(ipx)$, but may obtain a second set of averages linked to: $\int W^*(x)W(x) KE(x) dx$ which explicitly display invariance or the separate p terms. One may note in ((11)) that $a^*(p)a(p)$ is strictly positive and may be normalized to: $\sum_p a^*(p)a(p) = 1$ thus becoming a classical probability.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that spatial invariance and conservation of momentum are associated with a free particle and its dynamical probabilities $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ which follow from the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$. The eigenfunctions $\exp(ipx)$ constant are orthonormal over space ensuring conservation of momentum and $-id/dx$ is the spatial generator. The question becomes: What happens in the case of a single bound particle for which there is no spatial invariance or momentum conservation associated with $KE(x)$? There is only a $KE(x)$ which when added to $V(x)$ yields a constant energy at each x point. This constant energy is like part of rest mass

associated with a momentum of 0, but how does one handle the internal kinetic energy? Given that $-i\hbar d/dx$ is the momentum operator, $-1/2m\langle p^2 \rangle = \text{nonrelativistic case} = -1/2m \int d/dx W/d/dx / W$ for some function $W(x)$ which is a dynamic probability. All notion of invariance and momentum conservation is gone. Nevertheless $-d/dx$ is based on $-i\hbar d/dx$ which is associated with both. One may write $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ constant (constant needed to make $\exp(ipx)$ orthonormal).

We argue that even though $W(x)$ is not directly linked with momentum conservation or spatial invariance these ideas are still key in obtaining the physical observable $P(p)$. The same feature which makes $\exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$ zero when integrated over space for p_1, p_2 different makes $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ i.e. manifests the physical invariance of all x points. Thus one must take $W^*(x)W(x)$ and integrate over x so that only the physically invariant pieces and their weights survive and these weights are then the probabilities $P(p)$.

A more direct approach is to use $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ constant and $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ in the time-independent Schrodinger equation and collect coefficients of $\exp(ipx)$. This leads to an equation in p , i.e. displaying spatial invariance: $p^2/2m a(p) + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) = E_n a(p)$. Choosing the coefficient of $\exp(ipx)$ is mathematically equivalent to multiplying by $\exp(-ipx)$ or more generally $a^*(p)\exp(-ipx)$ and integrating over x . This leads to a spatially invariant type of equation with $a^*(p)a(p)$ terms which are positive and may be normalized to 1, thus representing classical probabilities $P(p)$. Thus the notion of $W^*(x)W(x)$ i.e. "taking the square" of $W(x)$ seems to be ultimately linked to the orthogonality of $\exp(ipx)$ s which in turn are linked to the spatial generator $-i\hbar d/dx$, spatial invariance and conservation of momentum.

References

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